

ON THE COMPOSITION OF UREA STIBAMINE

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The organo-antimonial constituents of urea stibamine have been found to be urea-*p*-acetamidophenylstibinic acid, *s*-diphenylcarbamido-4 : 4'-distibinic acid, and another organo-antimonial constituent, the constitution of which could not be ascertained.

Urea stibamine, introduced in India by Brahmachari (*Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1922, 10, 508 ; 1925, 13, 111) as a specific drug for the treatment of kala-azar, is formed by the interaction of urea with *p*-aminophenylstibinic acid (stibanilic acid). Regarded at first as a simple urea salt, it was later thought to be ammonium salt of 4-carbamidophenylstibinic acid, $\text{NH}_2\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{SbO}_3\text{H}(\text{NH}_4)$, a substance which has been synthesised by Niyogi (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 753). Subsequently, the detailed researches of Gray, Trevan, Bainbridge and Atwood (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1931, 108, B, 54) have indicated that urea stibamine is probably a complex mixture containing not only the monocarbamide but also *s*-diphenylcarbamido-4 : 4'-distibinic acid, $(\text{H}_2\text{O}_3\text{Sb}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{NH}\cdot)_2\text{CO}$, which they have synthesised by the phosgenation of *p*-aminophenylstibinic acid. They consider that *p*-aminophenylstibinic acid, normally employed in the preparation of urea stibamine, apparently contains varying quantities of its acetyl derivative. When heated with urea, such impure specimens of stibanilic acid partly react with the urea forming the above distibinic acid, and partly undergo hydrolytic fission with the production of antimonious acid. In the pure state the above distibinic acid does not form salts with any appreciable solubility in water. When antimonious and *p*-acetamidophenylstibinic acid, however, are present, as in urea stibamine, its solubility is increased owing to the action of these substances as protective colloids. According to Gray *et al.*, the reaction between urea and *p*-aminophenylstibinic acid proceeds according to the following course :

According to Gray *et al.*, the therapeutic activity of urea stibamine is largely due to *s*-diphenylcarbamido-4 : 4'-distibinic acid. In this connection it may be remarked that these authors have not tried to separate the different chemical constituents present in this drug, but have indicated the above course of reaction between urea and *p*-aminophenylstibinic acid on the basis of analyses of some samples of urea stibamine, prepared under different experimental conditions. It

has been therefore considered worthwhile at this stage to make attempts towards separation and characterisation of the different chemical constituents as present in this important drug.

The presence of free, uncombined urea in the urea stibamine and its influence on the toxicity of the drug have already been pointed out (Datta, Ghosh and Bose, *Science & Culture*, 1945, 11, 143). The percentage of free, uncombined urea varies, however, with different samples of the drug. It has also been shown that the drug contains some ammonium salt and that the replacement of the ammonium radical by hydrogen renders the compound insoluble in water. It has also been found that, besides some organo-antimonial constituents, urea stibamine contains varying quantities (though, very small) of antimonious and antimonous acids, the presence of which exerts a pronounced influence on the toxicity of the drug (Datta, *et al.*, *loc. cit.* Bose, Ghosh, Mitra and Datta, *Indian Med. Gaz.* 1946, 81, 13).

The following scheme, based on a study of the properties of the various constituents of the drug, as envisaged by Gray *et al.*, has now been adopted for the separation and characterisation of the various organo-antimonial constituents.

Following the above scheme, the organo-antimonial constituents of urea stibamine have been found to be (*vide* Experimental) (I) free, uncombined urea, (II) *p*-acetamidophenylstibinic acid, and (III) *s*-diphenylcarbamido-4 : 4'-distibinic acid. The fourth constituent (compound IV), as analysed, does not, however, conform to the formula of 4-carbamidophenylstibinic acid. Its exact chemical nature, however, could not be ascertained. It is difficult to ascertain whether 4-carbamidophenylstibinic acid is absent or present in the particular sample of urea stibamine examined and has been decomposed during separation of the constituents. In this connection, it should be mentioned that according to Gray *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) the concentration of urea in the preparation of urea stibamine plays an important part in the chemical composition of urea stibamine. According to these authors, a low concentration favours the formation of *s*-diphenylcarbamido-4 : 4'-distibinic acid, whereas, a high concentration of urea leads to the formation of 4-carbamidophenylstibinic acid. The resulting product (Urea Stibamine) in the former case has been found to possess pronounced trypanocidal action, whereas in the latter case, the product has been found to be comparatively inactive.

The percentage of the constituents mentioned above differs, however, with different samples and is dependent on the experimental conditions employed for the preparation of this drug. With regard to the constituent (II), it has been shown by Gray *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) that *p*-aminophenylstibinic acid, prepared according to published directions, invariably contains varying amounts of *p*-acetamidophenylstibinic acid. It has been subsequently shown by Datta, Ghosh and Bose (*Science & Culture*, 1945-46, 11, 385) that the ease with which commercial *p*-aminophenylstibinic acid reacts with urea is attributed to the presence of traces of the acetyl compound.

EXPERIMENTAL

Separation of the Organo-antimonial Constituents of Urea Stibamine : Isolation of Urea (I), p-Acetamidophenylstibinic acid (II) and s-Diphenylcarbamido-4 : 4'-distibinic acid (III).—A sample of well powdered urea stibamine (10 g.) was triturated and washed 2 to 3 times with hot absolute alcohol (total 100 c. c.). The alcoholic filtrate, on distillation under reduced pressure, yielded a solid which on crystallisation was proved to be urea (yield 0.3 g.).

The residue, left after treatment with alcohol, was dissolved in cold water and treated with well cooled hydrochloric acid (1%) till distinctly acidic to litmus, when a heavy precipitate was obtained. The precipitate was filtered and washed with cold water till free from hydrochloric acid. The solid was next treated with 20% caustic soda solution (ice-cooled) till just alkaline to litmus and the solution, after filtration to remove minute quantity of insoluble matter, was gradually saturated with chemically pure sodium chloride, when a heavy precipitate (P) was obtained, which was allowed to stand for some time and then filtered, and the filtrate (F) preserved for subsequent treatment.

The precipitate (P) was dried in a partially exhausted desiccator and then thoroughly triturated and washed 2 to 3 times with hot, anhydrous methyl alcohol (total 125 c. c.). The insoluble residue (R) was preserved for subsequent treatment. The methyl alcohol filtrate, on distillation under reduced pressure, left a brown solid which was next dissolved in water. The aqueous solution, when treated with cold hydrochloric acid (1%), yielded a brownish solid (II, 0.7 g.) which was thoroughly washed with cold water and dried in a partially exhausted desiccator. (Found: N, 3.99; Sb, 40.53. $C_8H_{10}O_4NSb$ requires N, 4.57; Sb, 39.82 per cent).

The residue (R) was dissolved in cold water and the solution, when treated with cold hydrochloric acid (1%), gave a precipitate which was thoroughly washed with water and dried, yield 4.8 g. It was purified by solution in cold alkali and precipitation by cold, dilute hydrochloric acid, when a brownish solid (compound III) was obtained which was dried in a partially exhausted desiccator. (Found: N, 4.26; Sb, 43.4. $C_{13}H_{14}O_7N_2Sb_2$ requires N, 5.05; Sb, 43.99 per cent).

The filtrate (F) was cooled in ice and then slowly acidified with cold dilute hydrochloric acid (1%), when a precipitate was obtained, which was thoroughly washed with cold water and dried in a partially exhausted desiccator, when a greyish solid (compound IV; 2.4 g.) was obtained. (Found: N, 3.0; Sb, 40.6 per cent). The analytical figures of this compound (IV) do not conform to the formula of 4-carbamidophenylstibinic acid and its exact chemical nature could not be ascertained.

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